

FindHeat - An Innovative Exploration Philosophy and Toolkit for Finding Geothermal Heat Efficiently and Sustainably

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ABSTRACT

FindHeat is a new Horizon Europe R&D project, involving six research institutions and five industry partners, that aims to transfer successful exploration and appraisal philosophies from more established industries to a broad range of geothermal plays. FindHeat will provide a modular toolkit of innovative software tools, geophysical exploration techniques, and new training materials to engage with a broad range of stakeholders from industry and society.

The key element for successful exploration and appraisal workflows, as demonstrated in the hydrocarbon and mineral industries, is the emphasis on conceptual models of geological processes that influence the occurrence and economic viability of exploration targets. Rather than adhering to a single geological concept, this approach facilitates resource assessments across multiple scenarios. A similar approach is expected to ultimately catalyse a paradigm

shift towards exploiting geothermal resources with inherently low technical and economic risks.

The FindHeat approach will be validated across eight geologically diverse geothermal plays. Specifically, we will demonstrate its technical and economic benefits arising from faster turnaround times for exploration and appraisal of geothermal resources, making better use of legacy data and non-invasive geophysical techniques, and constraining uncertainties with respect to the size of the heat source and the range of possible heat production rates.

Comprehensive social science research at the field sites will facilitate a new public place-based engagement process to earn public trust. Tailored training materials will be developed to disseminate the workflow to industry professionals and decision-makers from society.

1. BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

There are two key obstacles for realising the potential of geothermal energy. First, geothermal projects often have tight economic margins and a low return on investment. If exploration results (e.g., energy output

controlled by fluid abundance and production rate) are worse than expected due to the geological uncertainty inherent to geothermal systems, then the project is not financially viable. A sustainable business model therefore requires a high success rate for the development of geothermal projects. This is fundamentally different from oil and gas projects that may remain profitable even though production targets are frequently not met (Nandurika and Wallace, 2012). Second, public perception of geothermal energy is often not as positive as for other renewable energy sources, and hence support for developing geothermal energy is low (Reith et al., 2013). In particular, geothermal projects that failed economically were often underwritten by public finances while issues such as induced seismicity during the development of some geothermal resources have been well-publicised. Both have undermined public trust in the affected communities and beyond, casting doubts on whether geothermal energy can be developed safely and sustainably. Overcoming these two obstacles depends on resolving five interconnected challenges that will be discussed next.

1.1 Geological concept-based exploration

Successful geothermal projects require high temperature and high permeability, but knowledge of where these conditions can be found in the subsurface is limited. Exploration strategies in other industries (mining, oil and gas) usually follow a hierarchical, conceptual model-based exploration workflow.

For example, when exploring for hydrocarbons, the overarching concept is to establish the presence of a play consisting of a source rock, reservoir, and traps (cf., Jahn et al., 2008). The generic features of a play concept across different geological settings, i.e., the sedimentary basin and the location within the basin, are well established. The next level of hierarchy is the generic knowledge of which depositional environments contain reservoirs that are easier to produce (e.g., sandstones deposited in an aeolian environment), and which are more likely to encounter technical challenges (e.g., tight fractured carbonates). Generic knowledge of how these reservoirs could be exploited (e.g., offshore vs. onshore) also exists.

In other words, geoscientists know what “to look for” during exploration, i.e., how to locate the likely sweet spots where hydrocarbons could be produced at low technical and economic risk. Once such sweet spots are identified, the reservoir is appraised and characterised further to develop an exploitation strategy that is tailored for the site-specific geological features of the reservoir; this is the final level of the hierarchy. Such conceptual model-based exploration strategies, although not failsafe, were developed because hydrocarbons are a highly valuable commodity and incorporating best exploration practices was worth the

effort. A similar systems approach is also considered during mineral exploration (cf., McCuaig et al., 2010).

The situation in geothermal energy is radically different. Although play-based geothermal exploration has been proposed (Moeck, 2014), geothermal companies usually operate in one specific geological setting (e.g., volcanics vs. faulted basement rocks), which, together with tight economic constraints, prevents the development of generic concepts across all geothermal plays and resources, cross-fertilisation of knowledge, and ultimately the formulation of best-practice workflows that become corporate knowledge.

1.2 Agile modelling and simulation

Dedicated and industry-standard software solutions for geothermal exploration, appraisal, and development are limited and not fully integrated because they rely on individual, specialized tools. The lack of agility of workflows that utilise these software solutions renders them difficult to execute because turn-around times are usually long and hence hard to justify for geothermal projects. As a result, it is difficult to create a large number of digital models of different geothermal resources to develop the conceptual understanding of generic system behaviours or assess how geological uncertainties impact heat flow rates and exploitation strategies. Geological models of geothermal resources are often overly simplistic and geological concepts and associated exploitation strategies are not fully explored. Experience from hydrocarbon exploration and appraisal clearly shows that inadequate scenario testing of geological uncertainties and exploitation strategies exacerbates the technical and economic risks down the line (Bentley and Smith, 2008). This is ill-affordable when developing geothermal resources.

There is clear practical and theoretical experience that careful testing of geological concepts and exploitation scenarios leads to more economical and safer project developments. For example, industry experience from the Upper Rhine Graben has shown how more robust geological concepts prompted the re-evaluation of project development and resource exploitation strategies, resulting in lower costs and reduced technical risks (Dalmais et al., 2022). This approach enabled a reduction in drilling depth from 5 km to 2.5 km and cost saving of ~15 M€ per reservoir compared to a life-cycle cost of ~70 M€ for one of its geothermal power plants. The shallower depth also eliminated the need for stimulation (further cost saving of ~1 M€ per reservoir), which reduced the risk of induced seismicity and improved public perception. Furthermore, geological uncertainties were better constrained because the reliability of geophysical models increases with decreasing depth.

State-of-the-art open-source software tools developed in academia, such as GPU-accelerated geothermal heat flow modelling (Wang et al., 2023), accurate equations of state for high-enthalpy and superhot geothermal resources (Lamy-Chappuis et al., 2023), adaptive grid refinement techniques to model complex geological structures (Salinas et al., 2021), or fast and intuitive

geological modelling and flow assessment (Jacquemyn et al., 2021; Petrovksyy et al., 2023) have the potential to close these technology gaps but have not penetrated into geothermal exploration and appraisal workflows because their value for supporting robust decision-making processes is not fully established yet.

1.3 Tailored data acquisition

Acquiring new data for geothermal exploration is notoriously challenging due to budget constraints, access rights, time-consuming permitting, and disruption of local communities. Hence geophysical surveys such as 3D seismic surveys, while routine in the hydrocarbon industry, are still rare in geothermal energy.

Although there is evidence that 3D seismic data can help to constrain site-specific uncertainties and lead to better drilling decisions (Lueschen et al., 2010), there is no consensus as to which geophysical and geological data are most useful in constraining uncertainties during geothermal exploration. For example, while 3D seismic data were very useful to illuminate geological features in the carbonate sediments underlying the city of Munich and helped with well planning (Lueschen et al., 2010), it is unclear if seismic data can reliably image the faults which provide effective flow paths for geothermal fluids in crystalline basement rocks (Bächler et al., 2003; Fadel et al., 2022, 2023).

Electromagnetic tomography (EMT) is a very useful geophysical technique to image the heat source and infer flow pathways of geothermal fluids in high-enthalpy volcanic settings (Samrock et al., 2023), yet it is unclear if EMT can be reliably applied for characterisation of medium- and low-enthalpy geothermal resources or works in urbanised areas where the background noise is a challenge.

Similarly, it is unclear if short-wave infrared spectroscopy (SWIR) and drone imaging, which work well in certain geothermal settings (Glaas et al., 2019; Harvey et al., 2016), could be applied to a broader range of geothermal resources.

1.4 Techno-economics and value of information

Since acquiring and interpreting geophysical data is costly and its information content may be limited, knowledge of how additional datasets impact the economic risks of a geothermal project is also limited: the economic benefit of constraining geological uncertainties and predicting production rates of geothermal fluids with greater confidence through the acquisition of new geophysical data or reinterpretation of existing data still needs to be quantified. Traditional economic analyses of subsurface energy projects use metrics such as Net Present Value (NPV) and Internal Rate of Return (IRR) to quantify if a project is financially viable over its lifetime and justify investment decisions.

Modern value-of-information analysis methods that relate the economic analysis of a geothermal resource in terms of NPV and IRR to the geological uncertainties that control variability in the production rates and

temperatures of the geothermal fluid provide quantitative information about which geological uncertainties have the biggest economic impact when exploring and developing a geothermal resources (Daniilidis et al., 2017, 2021). This knowledge also provides the opportunity to quantify how valuable individual geophysical datasets are in not only constraining geological uncertainties but also in constraining the associated economic output.

1.5 Communication and training

Experience with geothermal energy varies greatly across Europe. Although in some countries, such as Iceland, public support is generally high and a well-trained workforce exists, this is often not the case, for example in countries such as Spain with little to no historical geothermal exploration.

In the latter type of country, public administrators, (local) governments, and societal stakeholders are hardly aware of which geothermal exploration activities need to be performed to develop geothermal energy safely and sustainably. Instead, a variety of external factors such as (social) media, local interest groups, and political parties shape public opinion, which eventually determines whether to agree with a project or not (Correlje et al., 2022).

Figure 1: Overview of the FindHeat consortium partners and location field sites.

The core challenge herein is that the communication between the technical experts and non-technical stakeholders, such as municipalities and local citizens, is often viewed as a one-way flow of highly biased information that cannot be trusted, which delays or even halts subsurface energy projects (de Vries et al., 2013). As traditional energy companies and consultancies expand into geothermal energy, and new

companies are founded, there is not only the need to retrain and upskill a technical workforce in the best practice of geothermal exploration but also the need to provide them with new communication strategies that enable a more transparent engagement process tailored to local needs and culture, which eventually earns trust with the broader public.

2. THE FINDHEAT APPROACH

The FindHeat consortium brings together long-standing expertise and innovation from industry and academia, covering geology, geophysics, engineering, social science, economics, communication, and technical training (Fig. 1). FindHeat has the aim to develop a new, integrated approach that enables users to appraise potential geothermal resources faster, at less cost, and at a higher success rate compared to the current state-of-the-art by shifting exploration towards geothermal resources and exploitation concepts that have inherently lower technical and economic risks. This aim will be achieved by

1. advancing and interconnecting agile, fast, and integrated exploration tools;
2. developing conceptual resource models for geothermal exploration;
3. analysing decision-making processes and their impact on project economics;
4. designing new methods for tailored training and communication;
5. developing a modular toolkit to release the FindHeat approach to end-users.

This FindHeat approach will be tested and demonstrated across a diverse range of eight geothermal sites (Fig. 2). This demonstration will include a detailed analysis of the economic and societal impact of faster, less costly, and less disruptive exploration. In the following sections, the individual components of the FindHeat approach will be discussed in more detail.

Figure 2: Summary of the key features and data for the field sites available to the FindHeat consortium.

2.1 Agile, fast, and integrated exploration tools

A fit-for-purpose workflow that is robust, fast, agile, and effective will be realised by connecting new software solutions, developed both in academia and industry, to low-cost and non-invasive geophysical techniques (Fig. 3). This workflow will enable us to define the conceptual, model-based exploration workflow by first testing it using synthetic data from literature in a well-controlled environment before demonstrating it, and iteratively refining it, using the data from the field sites.

The Rapid Reservoir Modelling (RRM) software (Jacquemyn et al., 2021) links a sketching interface with geological operators to build geologically consistent 3D models from a range of input data in a matter of minutes. RRM is particularly useful in

situations, such as geothermal exploration, where geological data is limited and uncertainties are high, because fast tools are needed to analyse and ultimately minimise exploration and development risks.

RRM also integrates flow diagnostics that provide direct quantitative evaluation of geological models (Petrovskyy et al., 2023). Flow diagnostics are controlled numerical experiments that can be conducted in seconds to obtain first-order insights into how geological heterogeneity and well locations impact flow behaviours (Møyner et al., 2014). By extending flow diagnostics to thermal processes, RRM can provide the initial real-time screening of the interplay between geology, well locations, and flow of geothermal fluids. This allows us to select representative geological models for further detailed geothermal simulations with DARTS (Wang et al.,

2023), CSMP++ (Lamy-Chappuis et al., 2023), and IC-FERST (Salinas et al., 2021) to investigate the most relevant geological and exploitation scenarios and test hypotheses, for example to analyse the impact of the connectivity of fluvial channels on expected flow rates in low-enthalpy geothermal systems.

RRM will be expanded to utilise data from WEB-AVO inversion of seismic reflection data, from non-invasive exploration methods (EMT, SWIR, drone surveys), as well as data representing the characteristics of fracture networks.

WEB-AVO inversion of seismic reflection data yields the elastic and rock properties that are needed to develop geological concepts that guide the exploration, appraisal, and development of geothermal reservoirs (Gonzales et al., 2022). For real-world applications in the hydrocarbon industry, WEB-AVO has been shown to lead to better drilling decisions where wells have 50% higher flow rates compared to other seismic inversion techniques.

EMT methods have been applied to image the electrical conductivity distribution in the subsurface (Samrock et al., 2023). Electrical conductivity is sensitive to the presence of fluids, temperature gradients, and conductive phases such as hydrothermal

alteration products. EMT methods have no environmental footprint, require short recording times, and are low-cost. Passive EMT methods are widely used for exploring high-enthalpy geothermal reservoirs, allowing us to identify the magmatic heat source, and to infer flow patterns, all of which help to de-risk exploration.

SWIR measures adsorption bands for different minerals in drilling cuttings (Glaas et al., 2019). It is a cheap and fast method that can be performed during drilling and works in poor well conditions. The combination of all SWIR spectra provides the mineralogical log for a given geological formation. From this log, specific minerals can be identified such as secondary clay minerals like illite that serve as proxies for the damaged and altered zones associated with existing fractures.

Drone surveys have been used in high-enthalpy systems (Harvey et al., 2016) but have not yet been tested and calibrated in low- and medium-enthalpy systems and close to operating geothermal plants. Drone surveys will be carried out to obtain imagery of fault patterns and thermal signatures above and in the vicinity of a geothermal reservoir. They will also be used to characterise fracture patterns at selected field sites.

Figure 3: Overview of the FindHeat technologies (clockwise from top left) showing RRM, a sketch-based modelling software for fast generation and testing of 3D geological concepts, WEB-AVO for inverting petrophysical properties including their uncertainties from legacy seismic data, heat and fluid flow simulations in the vicinity of a magma chamber showing the potential extent of a super-hot geothermal resource, EMT models that indicate the location and size of a magma chamber, and SWIR to characterise the mineralogy of drill cuttings and identify minerals that are proxies for fractures and flow zones in wells.

2.2 Conceptual resource models for geothermal exploration

The field sites (Fig. 2) are instrumental to refine the software tools, test the conceptual model-based exploration workflow, develop conceptual geothermal resource models, and simulate different exploitation strategies to predict their heat outputs and economic assessments under realistic conditions. The diversity of

the field sites allows us to develop different conceptual resource models and analyse how the geological uncertainties inherent to a given concept impact the assessment of possible heat outputs (exploitation configurations, rates, operation lifetime).

The superhot geothermal systems in Iceland form directly above the magmatic heat source driving

conventional high-enthalpy geothermal systems and, therefore, could enhance the conventional resource by either additional, direct production of superhot fluid, or by making additional magmatic heat available to the conventional resource via deep water injection into the superhot roots of the conventional system.

Fractures play a crucial role in enhancing reservoir permeability in the field sites in France, the Czech Republic, Iceland, and the UK. We will therefore focus on analysing and quantifying how uncertainties in fracture network properties and fault locations impact the extent of the heat source, the location of permeable zones that could be targets for drilling high-performing production wells that do not need to be stimulated, and variability in the expected production rates and temperatures. In the Netherlands and the Sherwood Sandstone in the UK, it remains unclear how sedimentary heterogeneities in fluvial channels (e.g., internal architecture of channel fills, channel geometry and connectivity) impact the advance of the thermal fronts during production, which geological features are barriers to flow, and which geological features create the risk of early breakthrough and rapid decline in production rates.

The field site in Spain has no exploration data yet. Here we will develop conceptual models of how this volcanic geothermal system could work, where the heat resource is located, and what its extent could be. Numerical simulations will be used to develop a preliminary set of resource scenarios.

Based on these scenarios, we will develop recommendations for further data acquisition to confirm or reject certain geological scenarios, constrain uncertainties, and determine if the geothermal system is viable to warrant further exploration and appraisal.

2.3 Decision-making and project economics

It is imperative to quantify the economic impact of a conceptual model-based exploration workflow that is enabled by the novel software tools and exploration techniques. We will consider real-world economic environments at the field sites that geothermal companies encounter to quantify how the FindHeat approach improves the economic viability compared to a current economic baseline for each site.

The techno-economic analysis will begin by establishing a common baseline for the value-of-information of existing exploration data and techniques. We will establish how data and techniques have influenced the understanding of the geothermal system and analyse subsequent investment decisions that impacted the development of the reservoir. This analysis will be deterministic so the quantification of economic uncertainties due to technical uncertainties (e.g., range of possible production rates, different drilling costs) and external factors (e.g., change in tax subsidies) will be limited.

We will then extend a novel approach to design an open-source, probabilistic techno-economic framework

that specifically accounts for the range of conceptual, technical, and economic uncertainties, and propagates them to the economic outlook of projects using probability (Daniilidis et al., 2017, 2021). This framework will enable us to analyse the field sites for validation and to repeatedly and seamlessly update the economic outlook as geological concepts are refined and uncertainties become better constrained when new geophysical data are collected and interpreted.

This approach allows us to quantify the technical and economic value-of-information of new datasets for updating and refining geological concepts, and hence the overall economic impact of a conceptual model-based exploration strategy.

2.4 Methods for tailored training and communication

To ensure that the FindHeat approach has impact in the technical community and wider society, we will develop tailored training and communication materials that help to upskill technical experts (geoscientists, engineers, lawyers, economists) working on geothermal projects, and to facilitate a trusted two-way communication with non-technical stakeholders (governments, local communities). While innovative training approaches for the former are well established, the latter requires a sound understanding of the perception of geothermal energy projects across different communities. The cultural diversity and different levels of experience with geothermal energy at the field sites allows us to tackle this issue in a comprehensive way.

By including local communities in important decisions, institutions can earn trust, reduce psychological biases and account for cultural impacts in this endeavour. We will execute a multi-step social science approach to improve public communication and understanding of public responses to geothermal exploration and development. We will analyse existing data and studies to reveal which general “local community” elements play a role in the public perception of geothermal energy and identify precursors to acceptance and resistance. Examples of such precursors include experience and familiarity with geothermal energy, culture, media, company image, and exposure to other geological industries in the vicinity such as mining or hydrocarbon production.

We will conduct empirical field research to compare impact of communication on public perceptions. Such field-based research allows us to formulate and test certain hypotheses for the public perception of geothermal energy, for example the positive perception that reliable, affordable, and low-carbon heat can be provided locally when trust in the operator is high that the right data have been acquired and the right workflows have been executed to ensure that induced seismicity is minimal (low-risk, high-reward scenario). The outcome of this analysis will then inform the design of communication strategies, specifically which

design elements (e.g., credibility, transparency, trust, balance) are effective in which context.

2.5 Modular toolkit

To enable broad dissemination of the FindHeat approach, we will integrate the individual tools and training and communication materials into a user-friendly and open-source modular toolkit, the FindHeat platform. This toolkit will enable knowledge sharing by ensuring that the key results can be accessed and utilised straightforwardly by end users. Where the platform relies on commercial software solutions (e.g., WEB-AVO) interfaces will be provided to these solutions to ensure that output can be used directly in the FindHeat platform while commercial background IP remains protected. The platform will be a web-based graphical user interface that provides a one-stop-shop for the different FindHeat technologies.

Figure 4: Play-based exploration approach for geothermal energy, adapted from the oil and gas industry.

3. FIRST RESULTS

The FindHeat consortium started in October 2024. The first step of our research was to establish a common

Figure 5: The main steps carried out during exploration for the eight field sites (Fig. 2).

4. SUMMARY

The FindHeat consortium brings together a transdisciplinary team of scientists and industry professionals who will develop a new exploration and appraisal approach for geothermal energy (Fig. 6). This concept-based approach will be tested across eight diverse field sites, ranging from super-hot geothermal resources to fractured basements and sedimentary

baseline of the exploration and appraisal approach used across the eight field sites (Janku et al., 2025), mapping them against a traditional play-based exploration approach from the hydrocarbon industry (Fig. 4).

Figure 5 presents a summary of the methods used during exploration and appraisal across the field sites. Most cases started by using legacy data to review and understand the regional geological context, followed by compiling an inventory of existing geothermal systems in the region (this was done for all commercial projects in the FindHeat portfolio). Although new data were collected for the geothermal systems to constrain uncertainties and estimate the geothermal resource (this was also done for all commercial projects), carrying out a full risk assessment or mapping geothermal sweet spots was surprisingly rare. Numerical simulations, which included probabilistic and/or statistical analyses often supported the assessment of the geothermal resource. In total, between 1.5 and 24 person months were invested to characterise the geothermal resources at the field sites.

This baseline analysis suggests that the current standards can be improved to enhance the efficiency and success rate of geothermal exploration, most notably by (i) constructing multiple geological scenarios and using numerical simulations early in the exploration phase to reduce uncertainties, assess risks, and guide data acquisition; (ii) cross-fertilisation of knowledge across different play types and utilising new technologies such as WEB-AVO, EMT, SWIR, or drone surveys etc. can help to establish best practices; (iii) gaps and inefficiencies in existing workflows can be addressed through better integration of software tools with specific emphasis on fast scenario testing, easy-to-use heat flow simulations, and modelling fracture networks.

sustainable exploitation of geothermal energy is feasible.

Figure 6: Overview of the FindHeat approach.

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